

Review Article

Post-partum cervicovaginal prolapse and its management in jersey crossbred cow

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Abstract

Cervico-vaginal prolapse is protrusion or eversion of vagina along with cervix through vulva, most commonly seen during last few weeks of pregnancy or several months before calving. The most common causes are; increase in intraabdominal pressure during pregnancy, hypocalcaemia and hormonal imbalance. A 24-year-old Jersey Crossbred cow, calved one day back was presented to large animal Gynecology and Obstetrics unit of Madras Veterinary College teaching hospital with a history of straining and edematous prolapse mass hanging from vulva. The case was diagnosed as cervico-vaginal prolapse. Animal was restrained and epidural anesthesia as given to reduce straining and for easy manipulation. Prolapse mass was reduced by the application of potassium permanganate solution (1:1000). After reduction, prolapse mass was repositioned or replaced back into normal position and finally retention suture was applied to prevent recurrence of prolapse. Post correction, animal was managed with antibiotics, antihistamine, analgesic, calcium and fluid therapy for three days.

Introduction

Cervico-vaginal prolapse is a disorder recognized by the protrusion of varying parts of the vaginal wall along with the cervix through the vulva and exposure of vaginal mucosa outside vulva [1]. This disorder is most commonly seen after parturition or last few weeks of pregnancy. The exact cause of this disorder is not fully known as it can occur due to various factors. The most common causes are; increase in intra-abdominal pressure during pregnancy, hypocalcemia, hormonal imbalance and excess perivaginal fat [2,3]. Post parturient

prolapse of the vagina of cattle is usually due to severe straining in response to vaginal trauma or infection after a serious dystocia. Initially animal will show signs of straining and protrusion of vaginal mucus membrane, in severe and delayed cases, whole anterior vagina and cervix protrude, large protruded mass becomes edematous and is prone to injury or infection which causes irritation and increase the expulsive straining effort [4, 3]. Eventually whole mass become ulcerated and necrosed, which may result in poor prognosis. If prompt attention is given, simple

measures often succeed [1]. The present article envisages the successful management of postpartum cervico-vaginal prolapse in a postpartum Jersey Cross bred cow.

History and Clinical Observation

A 24-years old jersey cross bred cow, with twelve number of calvings was presented at large animal Gynecology and Obstetrics unit of Madras Veterinary College teaching hospital with previous history of calving eight times, vaginal prolapse and underwent cesarian section two times. Animal shows signs of continuous straining, prolapse mass of cervix and vagina hanging outside vulva and vaginal mucous was exposed in the past one day. Animal was anorectic, increased body temperature (39.8°C) and anuria due to post-partum prolapse. Visual inspection of prolapsed mass revealed soiled, edematous and reddish cervico- vaginal mass. Animal exhibited severe and continuous tenesmus.

Diagnosis and Treatment

On the basis of history, clinical signs and clinical examination, it was diagnosed as the case of Cervico-vaginal prolapse. Low caudal epidural anesthesia (2% lignocaine, 5ml) was administered to reduce straining and for easy manipulation. The prolapse mass was cleaned with potassium permanganate solution and saline solution to reduce the mass. Prolapse mass was replaced back to normal position and vulval retention suture was then applied to avoid chances of recurrence of

prolapse [5]. Treatment was instituted with 25 % Dextrose 1.5 lit I/V and Ringer's Lactate 1.5 lit I/V, strepto-penicillin 12.5 mg/kg I/M, Chlorpheniramine maleate @ 0.5 mg/kg I/M, Meloxicam @ 0.2 mg/kg I/M, Vitamin B complex 10 ml I/V and calcium boro-gluconate 350 ml slow I/V for three days. On third day of treatment, clinical observation revealed all normal vital parameters and the patient was fully recovered.

Conclusion

Vaginal prolapse in cow is a hereditary, chronic, recurrent disorder. It is one of the reproductive disorders which cause economic loss to dairy farming. It is an emergency condition and should be treated immediately to avoid further complication. Increase in intra-abdominal pressure, excessive relaxation of pelvic ligaments and vaginal muscles due to increased estrogen level and hypocalcemia are the major causes of cervico-vaginal prolapse. Timely intervention will reduce complication, while as delayed case results in edematous, necrosed and inflammation of prolapse mass, therefore prognosis will be poor. Delayed in correction may cause some critical condition such as oedema, fibrosis, necrosis, septicemia and myiasis.

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